

The closing of the gender gap in the fourth industrial revolution with a feminist focus in Colombia

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Abstract

The abstract addresses the issue of inequity and the gaps of inequality affecting youth and women in rural areas of Colombia, particularly in the context of the fourth industrial revolution. These entrenched disparities have been exacerbated by historical and structural factors, limiting the access of these groups to educational, employment, and technological opportunities. The fourth industrial revolution, marked by technological advancements such as automation and digitization, presents both challenges and opportunities for these marginalized segments of the population. Recent research indicates that including youth and women in fields of study such as engineering can be a key factor in improving a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, for this to be possible, addressing the systemic barriers they face in accessing education and technical training in rural areas is essential. This implies the need to invest in education programs, vocational training, and digital literacy initiatives that provide them with the skills and competencies necessary to actively participate in the digital economy. This research will examine and disseminate the inequity and gaps of inequality affecting youth and women in rural areas of Colombia. It will explore how their inclusion in fields such as engineering can contribute to the economic growth and development of the country in the era of the fourth industrial revolution. To illustrate this point, successful case studies at both national and international levels will be analyzed, serving as inspiring examples and guides for academia, society, and government in the effort to close these gaps and promote inclusive development in Colombia.

Keywords: Systemic barriers; Gender inequality; 4.0 technologies; Microsexism.

1 Introduction

The 2030 Agenda set the goal of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), i.e. the member countries of the United Nations (UN) must meet these 17 SDGs by 2030 (Sánchez-Gómez, 2023). The Center for Sustainable Development Goals for Latin America and the Caribbean (COSD) has been measuring this compliance through the SDG Index since 2015 for this region. (CODS, 2020). This SDG Index follows the methodology of the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (UNSDSN, n.d.), validated by the European Commission (Sachs et al., 2019).

In the SDG Index, Colombia lagged in the fulfillment of SDG 5 on gender equality between 2015 and 2021 (Sánchez-Gómez, 2022), lag, which worsened in 2022 according to the SDG 2022 Index of the SDG CODS. Colombia went from an SDG 5 compliance score of 65.37 in 2015 to a score of 51.78 in 2022, showing an increasing lag in SDG 5 compliance. As a result, Colombia went from ninth position in SDG 5 compliance in the 2019 SDG Index to 13th position in the 2022 SDG Index (Centro de los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible para América Latina y el Caribe (CODS), 2023).

Colombia's lag in meeting SDG 5 on gender equity demonstrates the existence of a 30% gender gap according to UNESCO in 2019 (UNESCO, 2019). This gender gap must be addressed from a Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) approach (Merchán-Rubiano et al., 2023). Equity is understood as the elimination of barriers that impede

access to education for ethnic and cultural minorities and people with disabilities (Salmi & Bassett, 2014), and Inclusion ensures that everyone is integrated without any condition whatsoever (UNESCO, 2017).

In the historical context of Colombia, as well as in many other parts of the world, entrenched disparities have been forged that have profoundly affected the access of youth and women in rural areas to educational, employment, and technological opportunities. Historical factors such as violence, inequity in land distribution, and political marginalization have contributed to creating a disadvantaged environment for rural communities in Colombia.

Historically, women in Colombia have suffered discrimination and marginalization, a reality that is accentuated in rural areas. Deeply rooted cultural norms and traditional gender roles have restricted educational and employment opportunities for women throughout the country. This exclusion has been particularly evident in technical and technological sectors, where women have faced even greater barriers due to lack of access to resources and opportunities, a situation that intensifies in rural areas, where options for education and employment are even more limited (CEPAL, 2023).

Furthermore, limited access to technology and technical training has exacerbated existing disparities. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the lack of digital skills and the technological gap can leave rural communities, especially women and youth, lagging in the era of the fourth industrial revolution (OECD, 2019).

In summary, the historical context and systemic barriers in Colombia have created a challenging environment for youth and women in rural areas, limiting their access to education, employment, and technology. Addressing these systemic barriers is essential to promote social and economic inclusion throughout the country and close gender and age gaps in rural areas of Colombia (OECD, 2020).

The fourth industrial revolution not only presents significant challenges but also promising opportunities to close the gender gap in rural areas of Colombia. According to the World Development Report 2019 by the World Bank, in the era of the fourth industrial revolution, the demand for digital and technical skills is constantly increasing. This underscores the importance of investing in education and training programs tailored to the needs of women in rural areas (World Bank, 2018). On the other hand, entrepreneurship support programs, providing access to financing, mentorship, and support networks, can empower women to start and manage their businesses in the technology field. According to Colombia's National Development Plan 2018-2022, female entrepreneurship is essential to promote economic and social development throughout the country (Departamento Nacional de Planeación, 2018). Furthermore, promoting female role models in the field of technology and engineering can inspire girls and young women in rural areas to pursue careers in STEM. According to the Global Gender Gap Report 2021 by the World Economic Forum, creating mentoring programs and extracurricular activities that foster women's interest and participation in STEM can help overcome gender stereotypes and promote greater diversity in these fields (World Economic Forum, 2021).

In summary, by investing in education, training, entrepreneurship, and female role models, Colombia can harness the potential of women as agents of change and promoters of inclusive and sustainable development throughout the national territory. This will not only benefit rural women but also contribute to the country's overall economic growth and social development.

2 Methodology

The research question guides the researcher's interest in the scope of the research to answer the question formulated (Cifuentes, 2018) about in which cases the fourth industrial revolution in women closed the gender

gap? This question allows giving a value judgment on the effects of the fourth industrial revolution on the gender gap.

The research question is related to measurement it will be aligned with a positivist research method, which seeks to provide a causal explanation of the phenomenon studied. The methods related to positivist methods can be experimental and non-experimental (Cifuentes, 2018). Since the phenomenon studied is the gender gap, a measurement that occurs naturally, given that there is no control over these variables, therefore a non-experimental design is used (Sanchez, 2023; Sánchez-Gómez, 2023).

The causal case study is a non-experimental positivist method, that seeks to identify trends and causal relationships (Beach & Pedersen, 2016), to take the case as an instance in which there is a process that relates a house to an outcome.

3 Results

Recent research indicates that including youth and women in fields such as engineering can significantly improve a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, to realize this potential, it is crucial to address the systemic barriers they face in accessing education and technical training in rural areas. Investing in education programs, vocational training, and digital literacy initiatives can equip them with the necessary skills and competencies to actively participate in the digital economy.

The results were classified into 4 cases that show the closing of the gender gap in the fourth Industrial Revolution. The Cátedra Matilda represents the macro context of the most important engineering associations as LACCEI in Latin America and the Caribbean region, CONFEDI in Argentina, and ACOFI in Colombia. In the Colombian context are Mujeres en la Ciencia (Women in Science) of Sciences Ministry in Colombia, UNLab 4.0 (Laboratory of Industry 4.0) of Universidad Nacional, and Ingeniosas (Ingenious Women) of Universidad de los Andes.

3.1 Cátedra Matilda from ACOFI, CONFEDI y LACCEI

The main objective of the Matilda and Women in Engineering Latin American Open Chair is to encourage young women to pursue careers in engineering, believing in the professional and personal development and happiness of women in this field. It is an inspiring initiative that seeks to promote equal opportunities in the field of engineering (Páez Pino, 2020).

The Latin American Open Chair Matilda and Women in Engineering was founded by the Federal Council of Engineering Deans of Argentina (CONFEDI), the Colombian Association of Engineering Schools (ACOFI), and the Latin American and Caribbean Consortium of Engineering Institutions (LACCEI). These institutions joined forces to encourage young women to pursue careers in engineering, seeking to promote equal rights, opportunities, and spaces for women in this field. A significant collaboration to boost the professional development of women in engineering in Latin America (Páez Pino, 2020).

The objectives of the CAL Matilda are:

- Promote spaces for reflection and meetings around engineering to awaken interest in engineering careers as a profession.
- Strengthen the empowerment of girls and young women, recognizing and promoting the necessary skills for the exercise of engineering careers.
- Share knowledge and practices of the engineering profession to inspire young people in the career selection stage.

- Establish a language conducive to communicating the experiences of students or recent graduates in engineering careers, motivating curiosity for the field.
- Provide mentoring and supportive accompaniment to students at any school, work, or business level to reduce the gender gap in the personal, school, and work environment.

3.2 Mujeres en la Ciencia of Science Ministry in Colombia

This project, promoted by the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation, seeks to promote the participation of women in the scientific and technological field, offering scholarships, training, and research opportunities for young women and professionals in STEM areas (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). The program has contributed to reducing the gender gap in the scientific sector and empowering female talent in research and innovation in Colombia.

These are just some examples of the projects and programs that are being carried out in Colombia to promote gender equity and advance the fulfillment of the SDGs. Despite the progress made, much remains to be done to close the gender gap and ensure equal opportunities for all women in the country.

3.3 UNLab 4.0 of Universidad Nacional in Colombia

The UNLab 4.0 initiative, developed by the Faculty of Engineering at the National University of Colombia in collaboration with private sector companies, was launched in 2021 to foster an interest in engineering among youth, especially women, in rural areas of the country. The program sought to overcome entrenched prejudices and existing paradigms surrounding STEM careers to affect a cultural shift, implementing diploma and course offerings in territorial laboratories with a clear focus on innovation and 4.0 technologies to address local issues (López et al., n.d.).

The rural Colombian context presents particular challenges in terms of access to higher education and social pressure that perpetuates gender stereotypes regarding STEM careers. The UNLab 4.0 initiative emerged as an innovative response to address these barriers and promote equal opportunities in education in areas lacking public universities. The program was implemented nationally, selecting various municipalities in Colombia such as Puerto Wilches, Villavicencio, and Tauramena, and was based on active collaboration with private sector companies. Participants, mostly women, were engaged in specific diploma and course offerings designed to foster interest and participation in STEM disciplines.

The case highlights the participation of over 6,000 beneficiaries in diverse municipalities across Colombia. Notably, 70% of these youth currently hold an academic certificate from UNAL, and 65% of participants are women, challenging the traditional perception that engineering careers are exclusively male-dominated in these rural communities. A specific data point indicating that 30% of participants became interested in studying engineering after their program participation reflects a tangible impact. Furthermore, UNLab 4.0 support in university applications has led to at least ten women initiating their engineering studies in Bogotá, Bucaramanga, or Yopal.

The program has not only provided academic certifications to these youth but also changed attitudes and perspectives in a region where forming a family used to be the primary aspiration for many women after completing high school. The initiative has confronted entrenched social pressure and gender stereotypes, challenging the notion that engineering is a profession exclusively for men in these areas (López et al., n.d.).

3.4 Ingeniosas of Universidad de los Andes

This program seeks to encourage the participation of women in the field of engineering through academic activities, workshops, mentoring, and networking events. Since its implementation, the program has succeeded

in increasing the enrollment of women in engineering programs and improving female graduation rates at Universidad de los Andes (Cajiao et al., 2021).

The articulation between schools and universities is crucial to fostering the motivation of students in STEM careers for several reasons: identification of motivations, generation of impact, inspiration through role models, and strengthening of interests. This collaboration makes it possible to identify students' motivations when choosing a career path, which helps to design effective strategies to foster their interest in STEM. Collaborative engineering projects between high school and university students can have a positive impact on communities, motivating young people to see how their actions can improve the quality of people's lives. The ability for both girls and boys to be inspired by female engineers and scientists as role models can help break down gender stereotypes and motivate more students to pursue careers in science and engineering. Interacting with truthful information about engineering projects developed by peers in collaboration with universities can strengthen students' interests in STEM disciplines and show them the multidimensional impact they can have on their communities.

Engineering projects undertaken by high school students can have a positive impact on their communities in a variety of ways: solving local issues, raising awareness and changing behavior, generating intergenerational collaboration, empowerment, and skills development. These projects can address specific community issues, such as solid waste management, water management, and pollution, among others, offering innovative and sustainable solutions. By working on engineering projects, students can raise awareness about important issues, such as efficient water use or the importance of sustainability, which can lead to behavioral change in the community. Collaboration between high school and university students, as well as with companies and public entities, promotes intergenerational teamwork that enriches the proposed solutions and strengthens the impact of the projects in the community. By participating in engineering projects, students acquire technical, teamwork, problem-solving, and leadership skills, which contribute to their empowerment and personal development.

Finally, to inspire girls and boys to pursue careers in science and engineering, figures and role models of outstanding female engineers and scientists in the field are being used. Some strategies include Tesos Club, visibility of female roles in STEM, and role models. A Tesos Club has been created to highlight historical and iconic characters who have made important contributions to their disciplines, including women such as Lady Ada Lovelace, Hedy Lamarr, and other relevant female figures in science and engineering. The aim is to make visible and highlight the role of women in STEM through projects and activities that highlight their contributions and achievements in fields such as science and technology, to motivate new generations, especially girls, to pursue careers in these areas. The identification of female role models in science and engineering has been recognized as a fundamental strategy to guide and support girls on their path to academic and professional fulfillment in STEM (Cajiao et al., 2021).

4 Conclusions

The articulation between schools and universities is fundamental to motivating students to pursue STEM careers by identifying motivations, generating positive impact, inspiring through role models, and strengthening young people's interests in these disciplines. Engineering projects undertaken by college students can positively impact their communities by providing solutions to local issues, generating awareness and behavioral change, promoting intergenerational collaboration, and fostering empowerment and skill development in participants. These initiatives seek to break down gender stereotypes, inspire new generations,

and show the diversity of roles and possibilities that exist for women in fields such as science and engineering, thus promoting equal gender participation in these areas.

These initiatives seek to encourage young women to pursue engineering careers and promote equal opportunities in this field. Through programs, projects, and concrete actions, we seek to empower women in engineering, generate spaces for reflection, promote interest in engineering careers, and provide mentoring to reduce the gender gap.

Innovation is essential to address complex problems in the fourth industrial revolution, and this requires constant unlearning and relearning, questioning previous knowledge, and generating new solutions. Breaking paradigms and fostering critical thinking are key aspects of broadening perspectives and possibilities for action in personal and professional life, as well as in interactions with the environment. The development of skills such as critical thinking, creativity, communication skills, and collaborative work are fundamental to facing challenges in a context of constant change and technological evolution. The use of intellectually rigorous language and the elimination of double standards are tools for questioning and overcoming prejudices, structural values, and social norms that can limit the ability to innovate and solve problems effectively.

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